

Complexes of Salicylamide and Salicylanilide with Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II)

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In the present investigation two chelating agents salicylamide and salicylanilide have been employed for obtaining the complexes of the zinc(II), cadmium(II) and mercury(II).

SALICYLANILIDE has been reported to form the complex $VO(O.C_6H_4.CONHC_6H_5)_2$ with VO^{2+} and the complex $Mo.O_2(O.C_6H_4.CONH.C_6H_5)_2$ with MoO_2^{2+} by Syamal^{1,2}. Three isomeric complexes of copper(II) and chelates of iron(III), cobalt(II) and nickel(II) with salicylamide have already been reported by the authors^{3,4}.

Fig. I

Fig. II

The attempts to isolate the complex compounds by mixing the alcoholic solutions of the metal acetate or chloride and the ligand in the molar ratio 1 : 2

Fig. III

Experimental

Preparation of Ligands: Salicylamide was prepared by the method used by Rambacher and Miksch⁵. It was purified by dissolving it in dilute NaOH solution, treating it with activated charcoal and acidifying with cold dil. H_2SO_4 . Salicylanilide was prepared by the method already reported⁶ and purified by crystallizing it from alcohol.

Preparation of Complexes: Salicylamide or salicylanilide (0.02 mole) was dissolved in 25 ml of absolute alcohol and sodium hydroxide (0.02 mole) was added to it. The mixture was stirred for an hour and added to metal chloride or nitrate (0.01 mole) dissolved in minimum quantity of alcohol. It was refluxed for 10 hours on a water bath and under a calcium chloride guard tube. In the case of salicylamide the complexes separated out as insoluble in alcohol and filtered out. These were washed with deionized water several times to remove the contamination of sodium chloride or nitrate and

Fig. IV

ended in failure. These solutions yielded no complex under reflux.

then with absolute alcohol to remove impurities. The complexes in the case of salicylanilide being

soluble in alcohol were isolated by evaporating the filtrate.

Molar conductance measurements : The molar conductance data for these complexes were obtained by determining the resistance of the millimolar solution of the complex in nitrobenzene. It is given in Table 1.

of salicylamide as compared to the pure salicylamide indicates that the coordination has taken place through the nitrogen of the $-NH_2$ group also. So taking the phenolic oxygen into consideration the salicylamide ion has acted as a tridentate ligand although the three sites are not coordinated to the same metal ion. From the analytical data and IR

TABLE 1.—MELTING POINTS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Sl. No.	Name of the Complexes	m.p. °C	Δ_m mhos	Percentage			
				Found		Required	
				Metal	Nitrogen	Metal	Nitrogen
1.	Bis(Salicylamido) zinc(II)	170	0.28	19.20	8.40	19.29	8.31
2.	Bis(Salicylanilido) zinc (II)	140	0.32	13.00	5.57	13.30	5.73
3.	Bis(Salicylamido) cadmium(II)	No change upto 320	0.28	29.13	7.20	29.20	7.30
4.	Bis(Salicylanilido) cadmium(II)	169	0.48	20.81	5.10	20.90	5.26
5.	Bis(Salicylamido) mercury(II)	162	0.29	42.00	6.15	42.40	6.00
6.	Bis(Salicylanilido) mercury(II)	160	0.77	31.80	4.51	32.05	4.49

Infrared absorption measurements : The mull of the solid complex was prepared in nujol and the spectra were recorded on a Perking Elmer model 337, using sodium chloride optics.

Discussion

The results of elemental analysis for the complexes given in (Table 1) are in agreement with the general formula $M(O.C_6H_4.CONHR)_2$ where R is H or $-C_6H_5$.

The complexes of salicylamide with these three metal ions are insoluble in organic solvents and, therefore, these are expected to be polymeric in character. All these compounds are white crystalline solids and on exposing them to air over night, they are decomposed forming yellow, coloured products in the case of zinc(II) or cadmium(II) compounds but a black product in the case of mercury(II) complexes. The values of molar conductance of these complexes measured in nitro-benzene (Table 1) shows that these complexes are non-electrolytes.

On the basis of IR spectra the intramolecular hydrogen bonded chelate structure I has been proposed for salicylamide⁷ and the structure II for salicylanilide⁸ containing (N-H) group trans to the C = O group which in turn is chelated to the OH group through the intramolecular hydrogen bonding of the type $O-H...O = C$.

In the case of salicylamide and salicylanilide the coordination can take place either through the nitrogen atom (of the $-NH_2$ or $-NH C_6H_5$ group) or through the oxygen of the C = O group or through both of the atoms.

The carbonyl stretching frequency shifts towards the lower frequency side indicating that the coordination has taken place through the carbonyl oxygen^{9,10}. The decrease in the N-H bending or amide-II band frequency also supports the coordination through the carbonyl oxygen.¹¹ The lower N-H stretching frequency in the case of complexes

spectra it can be concluded that two salicylamide ions are bonded to each metal ion through the phenolic oxygen as well as the carbonyl oxygen atoms and this metal atom is linked to two such groups by the coordination through the nitrogen atoms of the $-NH_2$ groups. It leads to a polymeric structure which is formed by using the sp^3d^2 hybrid orbitals of the metal atoms. This explains the insolubility of these complexes in common organic solvents.

TABLE 2.—ASSIGNMENTS OF IR ABSORPTION BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF SALICYLAMIDE AND ITS COMPLEX COMPOUNDS

Assignments	Salicylamide (Nujolmull)	Complexes in nujol mull		
		Zn(II)	Cd(II)	Hg(II)
$\nu(N-H)_{as,m}$	3390	3372	3370	3320
$\nu(N-H)_{s,m}$	3185	3165	3166	3150
$\nu(C = O)$ or Amide-I	1685	1645	1640	1640
$\delta(N-H)$ or (N-H) bending or Amide-II	1640	1622	1625	1615

The compounds which are polymeric in nature can be represented by the common structure III.

TABLE 3.—ASSIGNMENTS OF IR ABSORPTION BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF SALICYLANILIDE AND ITS COMPLEX COMPOUNDS

Assignments	Salicylanilide in nujolmull	Sodium salt of salicylanilide in nujolmull	Complex compounds in nujolmull		
			Zn(II)	Cd(II)	Hg(II)
$\nu(N-H)$	3275	3335	3312	3305	3270
$\nu(C-O)$ or Amide-I	1619	1622	1600	1602	1605
$\delta(N-H)$ or (N-H) bending or Amide-II	1565	1560	1525	1530	1545

The lower N-H stretching frequency in the case of salicylanilide complexes as compared to that in sodium salt of salicylanilide can be explained on the basis of increased hydrogen bonding in the complex compounds.

The positive shift in the N-H stretching frequency in the complexes as compared to the free ligand itself supports that coordination has not taken place through the nitrogen. But the negative shift in the N-H stretching as compared to the free ligand in the case of the complex of mercury(II) is due to increased intermolecular hydrogen bonding which is supported by the higher (N-H) bending frequency as compared to that in complexes of zinc(II) and cadmium(II). Such hydrogen bonding has been reported in the case of complexes of benzamide with metal ions¹⁰. This behaviour of salicylanilide can be accounted for by the presence of benzene ring at the nitrogen atom which makes it less available for the coordination to the metal ions. Thus the ligand behaves purely as a bidentate chelating agent. It requires the tetrahedral hybridization for the

metal atom and this explains the solubility of these complexes in organic solvents. These complexes can be represented by tetrahedral structure (IV).

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